

A First Course in Medical Physics

Asif Shakur¹ ✉

¹*Department of Physics, Salisbury University, Salisbury, Maryland, USA*

Abstract

An experiment was conducted to test our initial hypothesis that Medical Physics should prove to be a very rewarding career option for physics majors. A graduate program in Medical Physics followed by residency training is a relatively new area of physics. In a nutshell, Medical Physics is the application of physics in a medical setting. The hypothesis was tested by developing a First Course in Medical Physics. The prerequisite for the first course in Medical Physics is a one-semester course in Modern Physics. We provide the outline of this course followed by a comprehensive inventory of questions that were administered on an experimental basis to the students. The answers are provided solely for the use of instructors who may wish to develop a similar course in Medical Physics for their undergraduate students. We are pleased to report that the hypothesis was validated. Our students have had phenomenal success in pursuing the Medical Physics program followed by residency. The purpose of this paper is to disseminate this among the wider physics community. We were so emboldened by the success of our students that we are planning to make this one-semester First Course in Medical Physics available to all our students in order to better prepare and invigorate future cohorts of our students.

Keywords: *Physics, Careers, Medical Physics, Residency.*

Introduction

A graduate program in Medical Physics followed by residency training is a relatively new area of physics which offers a very rewarding career for physics majors. In a nutshell, Medical Physics is the application of physics in a medical setting (American Association of Physicists in Medicine, n.d.). We first became aware of this some twenty years ago when serendipitously a flyer from VCU in Richmond, Virginia, was mailed to our department. We shared this with a senior who was clearly not receptive to this idea. After a few days of debating the pros and cons where we pointed out many more pros than cons, the student somewhat reluctantly agreed to give it a try. The rest, as we say, is history. The initial plan was to complete a master's degree. The student liked medical physics so much that he followed that with a Ph.D. and a residency program and is now extremely successful and happy at a hospital in Virginia. He thanks us profusely for advising him to pursue Medical Physics. We even invited him to make a presentation at a school of science seminar in a large auditorium. Recently he mentored another physics major who is now pursuing his residency in Medical Physics at Columbia University in New York. Yet another student at ECU has a podcast extolling the virtues of the Medical Physics residency (Standard Imaging, Inc., 2022). His only regret is that he did not follow our advice sooner and wasted a couple of years working in some other industry. He is glad that we had planted this idea which was swirling in his head for a few years.

Article History: Received: 26.06.2025 Revised: 28.07.2025 Accepted: 02.09.2025 Published: 04.09.2025

Citation: Shakur, A. (2025). A First Course in Medical Physics. *European Journal of Science and Modern Technologies*, 1(4), 74-79. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejsmt.2025.1\(4\).05](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejsmt.2025.1(4).05)

© The Author(s) 2025. Published by [AMO Publisher](#). This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted reuse, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Materials and Methods

We finally decided a few years ago to develop a one-semester course in Medical Physics to better prepare and invigorate future cohorts of our students. The prerequisite for the first course in Medical Physics is a one-semester course in Modern Physics. We tested the feasibility of this course by offering it as a special topics course (PHYS 499) to the student who is now pursuing his residency in Medical Physics at Columbia University in New York. Again, we were emboldened by the outstanding performance of this student in this course. Here we will provide an outline of this course along with a few representative questions and answers from the exams that were administered (Gibbons, 2019; McDermott, & Orton, 2018; Nappi, 2021).

Course Outline

Module I: Mathematics Review

Module II: Review of Basic Physics

Module III: Atomic Nuclei and Radioactivity

Module IV: Technology of X-ray Production

Module V: Physics of X-ray Production

Module VI: Interaction of Radiation with Matter

Module VII: Radiation Quantities

Module VIII: Radiation Detection and Measurement

Module IX: Medical Linear Accelerators

Module X: Central Axis Dose Distribution

Module XI: Calibration of Photon Beams

Module XII: Monitor Unit Calculations

Sample Questions and Answers

A patient is accidentally treated at 98 SSD instead of 100 SSD. The prescribed dose is 180 cGY for a single AP field. What dose did the patient actually receive? [Answer 187 cGY]

Prostate brachytherapy is a form of internal radiation therapy and is performed by carefully placing radioactive Iodine-125 seeds inside the prostate gland. The Iodine-125 seeds have a half-life of approximately 60 days and an initial activity of 10 mCi. What is the activity after 30 days? [Answer 7.1 mCi]

An electron makes a transition from the L (-11.1 keV) to the K shell (-70 keV) in tungsten. In what part of the EM radiation does the emitted photon reside? [Answer X-ray]

A radiation beam has a width of 24 cm at a distance of 100 cm from the source. What is the width of the beam at a distance of 140 cm from the source and what is the value of the angle θ ? [Answer 33.6 cm and $\theta = 6.8^\circ$]

The isotope $^{18}_9\text{F}$ is widely used for PET imaging. It decays by positron emission with a half-life of 110 minutes. What isotope does it decay to? [Answer Decays to $^{18}_8\text{O}$ (oxygen) + $^0_{+1}\text{e}$ (positron)]

A 4.0-mCi source with a 2.69-day half-life is implanted into a patient. The prescribed dose corresponds to 2.80×10^{13} disintegrations. Calculate the length of time after which the source must be removed. [Answer 3.2 days]

A 3-mm lead foil attenuates 75% of an x-ray beam. Find the HVL of the lead foil. [Answer 1.5 mm]

(a) Of the electron and the proton, which one does not exhibit a Bragg peak and why not?

[Answer The electron does not exhibit a Bragg peak. It follows a tortuous path. Only heavy particles like protons and alpha particles exhibit a Bragg peak.]

(b) What is the heel effect?

[Answer There is a gradient in intensity in going from the anode to the cathode side of the x-ray tube. The intensity is higher on the cathode side of the tube. The x-rays traverse more target material in escaping toward the anode side.]

(c) What material is a better absorber of neutrons than lead and why?

[Answer Hydrogen and paraffin wax. Elastic collisions with atoms of similar mass to neutrons cause the neutrons to lose kinetic energy and transfer their K.E. to the target nuclei.]

A beam of gamma rays is directed toward a block of concrete that is 2.4 m thick. Concrete has a density of 2.4 g/cm^3 . Each gamma-ray photon has an energy of 3.0 MeV. On the far side of the concrete block, the intensity of the beam is found to have been reduced to 5.52×10^{-10} of its initial intensity. What is the mass attenuation coefficient for 3.0 MeV photons in concrete?

[Answer Mass attenuation coefficient = $0.037 \text{ cm}^2/\text{g}$]

The LET of a 2.5 MeV α particle is $20 \text{ keV}/\mu\text{m}$. Find the LET of a proton having the same speed as the alpha particle. What is the range of the proton in mm? [Answer The LET of the proton is $5 \text{ keV}/\mu\text{m}$ and the RANGE of the proton is $126 \mu\text{m}$.]

What is the maximum kinetic energy that can be imparted to an electron by a Co^{60} 1.25 MeV photon? What is the range of such an electron in water? [Answer From Compton scattering at 180° , the photon loses 83% of its energy or 1.04 MeV to the electron. The range of such an electron is 0.52 cm.]

A beam of 10-MeV photons interacts with water. The photon fluence is $4.0 \times 10^{14} / \text{m}^2$ in a small volume at a particular location.

(a) What is the energy fluence in units of J/m^2 ?

[Answer $6.6 \times 10^2 \text{ J}/\text{m}^2$]

(b) There is CPE in the given volume and the absorbed dose is 1.00 Gy. What is the collision kerma in Gy?

[Answer For CPE, collision kerma = absorbed dose = 1.00 Gy!]

A 10 g mass of tissue is uniformly irradiated and receives 1 cGy of absorbed dose. How much energy is absorbed by 5 g of this tissue? [Answer $5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ J}$]

A 0.6 cm^3 Farmer chamber receives a 1 R exposure. The air inside the chamber is at 22°C and 760 mm-Hg pressure. Calculate the charge in nC produced inside the chamber if the cavity is in CPE. Take the density of air as $1.21 \times 10^{-3} \text{ g/cm}^3$ inside the chamber. [Answer 0.187 nC]

(a) Why are klystrons used in some linacs and magnetrons in others?

[Answer Magnetrons are used in low energy standing wave linacs and in traveling wave linacs. Klystrons are used in standing wave linacs with energies above 12MV. A magnetron for a linac costs \$30,000 whereas a klystron costs \$70,000.]

(b) S-band microwaves have a frequency of 3.0 GHz. Each cavity in the accelerator waveguide is $\frac{1}{2}$ of a wavelength long. The energy gain is 0.6 MeV per cavity and the maximum electron energy is 18 MeV. How long is the waveguide? [Answer 150 cm]

(a) Why is a transmission target used for a linac and a reflection target used for a low-energy diagnostic x-ray machine?

[Answer x-ray production is peaked in the forward direction]

(b) How much does the beam current for a linac change in going from x-ray mode to electron mode?

[Answer 1/1000]

For a prostate “seed” implant, I-125 seeds ($t_{1/2} = 60$ days) with an activity of 0.350 mCi are needed on the day of the implant. The seeds are to be delivered one week prior to the implant. What activity should the seeds have on the day of the activity?

[Answer 0.38 mCi]

For high-energy photon beams incident upon a medium, why doesn't the dose have its maximum value at the surface? Recall that the photons are steadily attenuated as the depth increases.

[Answer This is “skin sparing”]

The air inside an ionization chamber is initially at STP. The temperature of the air rises 3°C and the pressure decreases by 20 mm-Hg. What is the percentage change in the ion chamber reading? Does the reading increase or decrease? [Answer 3.6% decrease]

An x-ray technologist makes an exposure at 100 kVp, 100 mA, 0.5s. The image is blurry because the patient is fidgeting. The technologist reduces the time to 0.2s and keeps the same kVp. What mA should be chosen to keep the image darkness the same? [Answer 250 mA]

A patient is to be treated isocentrically with 6MV whole brain radiation using a lateral field on the Mevalac. The collimator jaws are set to 20 cm \times 26 cm. The MLC blocked equivalent field size is = 15.8. The dose to be delivered by this beam is 100 cGy on the central axis at a depth of 7.5 cm. Refer to the data table to calculate the required MU. [Answer 105 MU]

A dose of 180 cGy is delivered to a depth of 7.0 cm on the central axis with a 6 MV beam having a field size $10 \times 10 \text{ cm}^2$ and SSD = 100 cm. What is the dose deposited at a depth of 12 cm on the central axis? [Answer 139 cGy]

Medical Physics Capstone Project

We have also had many students do their capstone project in Medical Physics. The title of one capstone project was “Analyzing Equivalent Treatments from Linear Accelerators and Gamma Knives”. There are two popular methods of treatment, linear accelerators and gamma knives. Linear accelerators are often very useful when providing treatment for cancers that may not involve the brain such as lung cancer, but they are not as effective as gamma knives when treating brain related issues. Gamma knives are particularly useful in situations like these where there are metastases or other issues in the brain because they limit radiation exposure to healthy tissue. The poster for this Capstone Project is depicted in Figure 1 below.

Analyzing Equivalent Treatments from Linear Accelerators and Gamma Knives

Introduction

What is Medical Physics?

- Medical Physics is a subfield within physics that seeks to treat human diseases and growths through the use of various treatments. Within the field of Medical Physics, there are different areas of study to which a physicist could conduct research including radiation therapy, medical imaging, nuclear medicine, and radiation protection.¹

What tools are used to treat cancer in Radiation Therapy?

- There are two popular methods of treatment, linear accelerators and gamma knives. Linear accelerators are often very useful when providing treatment to cancers that may not involve the brain such as lung cancer, but they are not as effective as gamma knives when treating brain related issues. Gamma knives are particularly useful in situations like these where there are metastases or other issues in the brain because they limit radiation exposure to healthy tissue.

Purpose/Method

Goal and Execution

- Overall, the medical physics community has produced a significant amount of literature and research on treatments from linear accelerators and gamma knives. One research paper explored the dosimetric comparison of gamma knife and linear accelerator-based fractionated stereotactic radiotherapy plans for reirradiation of large recurrent glioblastomas, a type of aggressive cancer within the brain. In this research it was generally found that there is a decrease in radiation exposure to normal brain tissue with the use of gamma knife treatment plans.² My goal was to see if these results would be consistent when comparing several different patients, with various conditions affecting the brain, from Johnston Willis Hospital. This would allow for more generalized evidence of the effectiveness of using a gamma knife compared to linear accelerators in the context of problems that are in the brain.
- In order to do this, I created comparisons between the two different types of treatment by focusing on values such as target coverage, conformity index, and mean dose which are all useful in assessing precision and efficiency of treatment.

CT/DVH Patient 1

References

- Wikipedia The Free Encyclopedia
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Medical_physics
- National Library of Medicine
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3055238/>
- SlicerRT Toolkit
<https://slicer.org/>
- RadiationInfo.org
<https://www.radiationinfo.org/en/faq/faq-10.html#q10>
- Cancer Centers of Southeast Oklahoma
<https://www.ccsomh.com/department/brain-tumor/>
- The Mayo Clinic
<https://www.mayoclinic.org/brain-tumors/brain-tumors/radiation-therapy/about/pcr-2018679>
- BrainSelling
<https://www.brainselling.org/en/our-uses/brain-tumors/understand-radiation-therapy-treatment-for-brain-tumors-how-does-radiation-therapy-work/>

Results and Conclusions

Upon analysis, I discovered that the findings of the research from analyzing gamma knife and linear accelerator-based fractionated stereotactic radiotherapy plans for reirradiation of large recurrent glioblastomas can in fact be generalized. For instance, in "Patient 2" that I analyzed, there was nearly four times the radiation exposure from the LINAC treatment vs the gamma knife treatment to the brain stem (See highlighted in red). Of course, this kind of analysis depends on each patient and there will be variation based upon the treatment plan. This was partially due to the location of the target area, but ultimately demonstrated the usefulness and precision of a gamma knife for these kinds of treatments. Unsurprisingly, it was found that the LINAC had a better conformity index compared to the Gamma knife when analyzing treatment plans. In the bottom right is a full analysis of "Patient 10" as an example. It is also important to note that both patients received full target coverage regardless of treatment type.

$$TC = \frac{TV_{PV}}{TV}$$

Figure 3.2

$$GI = \frac{PV_{ORG}}{PIV}$$

Figure 4.3

$$Paddick\ CI = \frac{TV_{PV}^2}{TV \times PIV}$$

Figure 5.2

Target coverage is found by dividing the prescription isodose volume (PIV) by the target volume (Figure 3). The conformity index is found by dividing the target PIV squared by the product of target volume and PIV (Figure 4). Finally, the gradient index is found by dividing the patient volume involving dosage by the PIV (Figure 5). Upon analyzing these visualizations and values, I will be able to draw conclusions on both treatment types from all patient data analyzed.

Figure 1. Capstone Project: Gamma Knives

Results

Our working hypothesis that Medical Physics should prove to be a very rewarding career option for physics majors was found to be overwhelmingly correct. Our students have had phenomenal success in pursuing the Medical Physics program followed by residency. The first student liked medical physics so much that he followed that with a Ph.D. and a residency program and is now extremely successful and happy at a hospital in Virginia. He thanks us profusely for advising him to pursue Medical Physics. We even invited him to make a presentation at a school of science seminar in a large auditorium attended by faculty and students from many disciplines. Recently he mentored another physics major who is now pursuing his residency in Medical Physics at Columbia University in New York. Yet another student at ECU has a podcast extolling the virtues of the Medical Physics residency (Standard Imaging, Inc., 2022). His only regret is that he did not follow our advice sooner and wasted a couple of years working in some other industry. He is glad that we had planted this idea which was swirling in his head for a few years. We have also had many students do their capstone project in Medical Physics. The title of one capstone project was “Analyzing Equivalent Treatments from Linear Accelerators and Gamma Knives”. There are two popular methods of treatment, linear accelerators and gamma knives. Linear accelerators are often very useful when providing treatment for cancers that may not involve the brain such as lung cancer, but they are not as effective as gamma knives when treating brain related issues. Gamma knives are

particularly useful in situations like these where there are metastases or other issues in the brain because they limit radiation exposure to healthy tissue.

Discussion

We started this research with the working hypothesis that a very rewarding career option for physics majors may well be the nontraditional and relatively unknown subdiscipline of medical physics. We were cued into this serendipitously. We followed our hunch and pursued this avenue. We developed a first course in medical physics and administered it on an experimental basis. The prerequisite for the first course in Medical Physics is a one-semester course in Modern Physics. The results were spectacularly phenomenal. The student was accepted into the residency program at Columbia University. We were so emboldened by the success of our students that we are planning to make this one-semester First Course in Medical Physics available to all our students in order to better prepare and invigorate future cohorts of our students.

Conclusion

A graduate program in Medical Physics followed by residency training is a relatively new area of physics which offers a very rewarding career for physics majors. In a nutshell, Medical Physics is the application of physics in a medical setting. Our students have had phenomenal success in pursuing the medical physics program followed by residency. The purpose of this paper is to disseminate this among the wider physics community. We were so emboldened by the success of our students that we have developed a one-semester course in Medical Physics to better prepare and invigorate future cohorts of our students. The prerequisite for the first course in Medical Physics is a one-semester course in Modern Physics. We have provided an outline of this course along with a few representative questions and answers from the exams that were administered. Many of our students also do their capstone project in Medical Physics.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

References

- American Association of Physicists in Medicine. (n.d.). *Education*. AAPM. Retrieved September 3, 2025, from <https://www.aapm.org/education/>
- Gibbons, J. P. (2019). *Khan's The Physics of Radiation Therapy* (6th ed.). Lippincott Williams & Wilkins. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mp.14575>
- McDermott, P. N., & Orton, C. G. (2018). *The Physics & Technology of Radiation Therapy* (2nd ed.). Medical Physics Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1118/1.3594546>
- Nappi, L. M. (2021). *Radiation Therapy Calculations Manual*. Amazon Digital Services LLC. ISBN 979-8784161482.
- Standard Imaging, Inc. (2022, August 23). Medical Physics from the Resident's Desk with Rainor Connor [Audio podcast episode]. In *Out of the Gray (Gy) Podcast*. Standard Imaging. Retrieved September 3, 2025, from <https://www.standardimaging.com/out-of-the-gray-podcast/medical-physics-from-the-residents-desk-with-rainor-connor>

